

OPEN SCIENCE PLATFORMS AS DATA REPOSITORIES FOR AUTOMATED SUMMARIZATION

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Abstract

Although open science platforms play a significant role in making research findings freely available, the search for relevant information can take a significant amount of time. This paper outlines a concept for automatic summarization that is intended to speed up and simplify this selection process by creating a summary from recent publications. The idea is to use automatic summarization to give users an overview over recently uploaded content relating to their field(s), coupled with intelligent selection of content that is relevant to the user's interest. In this, it takes into account user preferences regarding domain, timeframe, and summary length. The hope is that by utilizing notification systems and/or newsletters with these summaries, users will find staying up to date on research more time-efficient and easily accessible.

INTRODUCTION

Open science platforms and the content they provide play a considerable role in making research accessible to other scientists, as well as to the interested public. Depending on the platform, its content can range from published papers and presentations to data sets or tables. However, with the amount of material that is continually added, often of miscellaneous types and from a variety of scientific disciplines, keeping track of new research can be time-consuming and troublesome, and searching for content of interest can be challenging.

While the focus of automated summarization is frequently on singular texts, the automatic creation of multi-document summaries is a possible way of creating a more effective way of finding relevant research among a wide array of publications. In the concept described here, the user can choose to receive a summary that includes the core findings of a user-specified subgroup of articles rather than being required to actively search for potential articles of interest.

To this point, the concept places a strong emphasis on personalisation of the automated summary. The paper outlines two different ways of selecting the text sources of interest, either by predefined topic(s) or by user selection.

It is necessary to state that this concept for automated summaries is intended to help with pre-selection and gaining an overview only, it is not supposed to replace reading the papers in their entirety. Depending on their level of interest, the user will likely still have to go to read specific content to get in-depth knowledge. However, the summary allows

them to choose papers more easily than by title, and it should give a sufficient overview to those who simply want to get a rough idea of recent developments in a specific field of research.

RELATED WORK

Automated text summarization has been a topic of interest for years, with entire conferences and/or conference tracks dedicated to its research; some of the most used data sets, for example, originated from Document Understanding Conferences (DUC) in the years 2001 to 2007 [1], and the Text Analysis Conferences (TAC) summarization track from 2008 to 2011, as well as 2014 [2]. In the years since, there has been much progress in the field, particularly after the first creation of a pre-trained, transformer-based architecture - BERT [3] - which has led to an increasing number of modified and extended versions thereof. However, larger data sets often prioritise news articles, such as Multi-News [4] and Newsroom [5]. On the other hand, the creation of summaries for scientific texts tends to present an expensive problem in terms of time expended, since the so-called "golden" or reference summaries are usually still manually written by humans.

Because of this, finding large training datasets which provide scientific texts as well as a summarization thereof can be challenging. Although the DUC and TAC data sets consist of papers and their summaries, they are generally limited in size, which may present problems for machine learning tasks. One recent paper by DeYoung et al. [10] introduced a data set for automatic summarization of medical studies which contains both scientific documents and summaries created from systematic literature reviews.

Furthermore, a substantial amount of research focuses on the summarization of single, shorter texts, as opposed to creating a single summary for multiple inputs. In particular, scientific texts, such as journal articles, are usually longer and thus require a different approach from inputs such as news articles. The further the input differs from that, the harder it becomes to obtain a satisfactory result, as was found when Dima et al. researched the application of NLP for technical text [6]. Even with scientific papers, which do face quite the same difficulties as technical text, problems such as redundancy may present challenges to create optimal summaries. Special considerations do not only have to be made for the used algorithms and models, either, but begins at the choice of format for the summary, for which purely textual forms may not always be the best choice.

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Open science platforms such as Zenodo¹ and INSPIRE² provide access to a wide range of content that can sometimes be overwhelming. Depending on the accepted file types on the platform, the available content may take many forms. From presentations over research papers to images or entire data sets, users can freely access a variety of material. In addition to this, Open Science Platforms often do not limit the provided content to only one field of science, which can present further difficulty in finding relevant research. Some platforms show keywords that can be searched with, allowing for the selection of a subset of connected articles. However, even then, it is usually necessary to access every record to be able to read their abstracts.

Due to this, and the amount of content available, it can become cumbersome to keep track of recent findings in one's topic(s) of interest and get a proper overview of new material. To get a proper idea, a user would need to first search for their topic of interest, potentially in a way that depends on the platform's search system, and then access a large number of records to reach all abstracts. For many people, this is simply inaccessible due to time constraints. However, at the same time, this wealth of resources presents a chance for research to thrive and progress rapidly by more easily building on each other's work.

Due to the usefulness of automated summarization, the creation of such summaries is a highly researched field in a variety of domains. Although much of the research has been done using news articles for data sets [8], [7], in recent years there has been an increasing number of publications that specifically focus more on scientific problem cases. While Xiao et al. showed results using a variety of data sets, some of them including scientific papers [9], another study focused on medicine in particular, where the literature review of scientific studies can take up a significant amount of time [10]. While a summary of a large number of papers cannot replace reading the papers themselves, it is possible to get an overview over the key points and overlaps, as well as distinctions between the papers, which can help with further selection of material to be read in-depth, or to get a first insight into the current state of a field that may be new to the reader. Depending on the application of the system, this can be more focused on single-document summarization or multi-document summarization, as well as abstractive or extractive summarization. Different approaches show different results depending on the application domain. In this case, focus will lie on multi-document summarization, where the objective will likely require abstractive summarization to form a coherent text from the input.

Another possibility for the automated creation of summaries is the use of knowledge graphs, where the problem can generally be split into two phases, information extraction (into the graph) and text creation (from the graph). In recent research, a phenom-based approach has for example been used to create news articles from legislative proceedings [13].

Pasunuru et al. created a method that allowed for the inclusion of graph information into the encoder/decoder-based model used to summarise multiple documents [15].

USER-FOCUSED AUTOMATED SUMMARIZATION

The goal for the concept introduced in this paper is to mitigate the problem of information overflow and attempt to make the utilisation of open science platforms more attractive to both the scientific community and the wider public. The idea is to use automatic summarization to give users an overview over recently uploaded content relating to their field(s) of interest, coupled with intelligent selection of content that is relevant to the user's interest. Ideally, the functionality would be introduced as an additional part of a notification/newsletter infrastructure. This will eliminate both the need to search for fitting content and reduce the time necessary to read through them in search of their key findings.

As such, when it comes to the utilisation of open science platforms as data repositories for an automatic summarization system, the following main requirements can be defined:

- Selection of relevant text sources
- Extraction of key information from each source
- Summarization for a specified distribution technology
- Personalisation through user specification

Consequently, the user would be able to get a firm idea of which papers are of further interest from reading the summary and, if they want to gain deeper understanding, then go on to read only those. In this context, it should be mentioned that the intention of this system is not to make any sort of decision on whether the information in the papers is considered to be scientifically sound or correct, but rather to accurately represent the content of the papers themselves.

With the specified high-level requirements the components and interactions can be roughly illustrated as in Figure 1. The two points of particular interest for the proposed system are the summarization system and the user specification, which can both be approached in a variety of ways, briefly outlined in the following sections.

Concept Proposal

To implement the pre-selection, the user would first specify their area(s) of interest, after which an algorithm would use this information to determine appropriate material on the open science platform. It may be useful to specify how far back the algorithm should look to avoid out-of-date information.

After this, the inputs - much of which usually comes in PDF form, as is the norm for published papers - go through a preparation stage, during which any text is extracted and prepared for the summarization process.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/>

² <https://inspirehep.net/>

Figure 1: Diagram of an open science platform-based automatic summarization system

The extracted text then needs to be summarized, with the particular goal of stressing similarities and differences between the papers, if possible. Reading the single summary should give enough information for the user to be able to decide which papers, if any, are of further use to their research or just in general of interest. Depending on the user, the ideal summary length may be different, as well as the time between two newsletters.

For short summaries, it may be of interest to summarize the papers in one sentence, similar to the work presented by Cachola et al., in which they created TLDR versions of scientific texts [12]. An ultrashort summary of multiple papers may only need to be put together from one-sentence summaries of each paper.

The idea, however, is to find a medium between ultrashort and full-text versions of papers. In this, the summary is intended to also briefly outline where the summarised papers overlap - for example in methods used, algorithms utilised, etc. This could be where alternative modes of output, such as tables, may be of use.

Finally, this summary is communicated to the user through a previously specified way, depending on the available communication channels, such as email or app notification.

Automated Summarization

Though it is only shown as one component in Figure 1, the summarization system itself can once again be split into two main tasks: key information extraction and text creation.

Personalisation

As partially and briefly mentioned in the section before, this system is intended to provide a number of possibilities for personalisation. In the first place, the topic selection for the papers should be according to the user's selected interests. This presents the problem of how granular this selection should be; specifying singular keywords can present difficulties both due to the subjectivity of a paper's keywords and the possibility of typos, etc. Additionally, some sources may not have keywords at all, particularly in cases where other material than the papers is supposed to be part of the summarized content.

However, choosing an entire field such as Physics encompasses a wide array of subtopics, of which not all may be relevant. The solution may be platform-dependent. If there are mandatory categories when uploading content, this may later be useful to group the papers. Or, it may be necessary to categorize the papers according to topic before the actual summarization task can take place if no simpler solution for the problem can be found.

Secondly, as mentioned before, the length of the summary should be according to the user's preference. While some may prefer very short and concise summaries used only to keep vaguely up to date on evolving research directions in a field, others may wish to use it as a tool for pre-selection of reading material. Depending on the use case, the ideal summary may look different.

CONCLUSION

Open science repositories present a chance to build on each other's work in a way that can only further scientific progress. Furthermore, it allows anyone interested insight into what is currently happening in research. However, due to the wealth of information available, it can be difficult to keep track of new material of interest for the user. The proposed solution aims to automatically select content that is relevant to the user's interest, as well as to use automatic summarization to make the selected research more accessible by cutting down the time necessary to get an overview over relevant recent findings and communicating the resulting summary to the user directly.

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